

RECYCLABILITY OF WASTE CORD OF SYNTHETIC FIBERS AS MATRIX MATERIAL OF THERMOPLASTIC HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The hybrid composites were molded by using the waste cord of synthetic fabrics as a matrix material, in which continuous glass and carbon fibers were used for the reinforcements and were fed into the injection molding machine directly together with the waste cord. The measured tensile strength and modulus of the molded composites were much larger than those for the matrix material, and increases with increasing contents of carbon fibers. It is concluded that the molding system devised here is effective for the material recycle of the waste cord of synthetic fabrics.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the establishment of recycling technique for industrial waste products was required because of environmental protection. For example, the recycling technique for some plastic products such as PET bottles have already been developed [1,2]. On the other hand, the textile industry takes a growing interest in a recycling system of waste cords of fibers which are produced during the manufacturing process of the textile fabric, non-woven fabric, fishing net, &c.. However, because of a lack of effective recycling technique, most of these waste cords are burnt up or buried in the ground now.

Meanwhile, for the variety of recent engineering requests, many researches related to the development of new materials are carrying out actively in many fields. Especially, many attentions are focused upon the development of fiber reinforced composites such as GRP and CFRP with superior mechanical properties. Recently, the attention is shifted to the thermoplastic composites from the thermosetting composites because of the higher recyclability of the thermoplastic matrix resin. For example, the stampable sheet with long glass mat is widely used in the automotive component such as a bumper beam, and the researches related to its recyclability have been carried out actively [3].

In consideration of above circumstances, the recyclability of the waste cord of thermoplastic synthetic fibers as a matrix material of fiber reinforced composites was discussed in this paper by proposing a simple injection molding system. Especially, the carbon/glass hybrid composites were molded, and their mechanical properties were investigated.

USED MATERIALS

During the weaving process of synthetic fabrics using the water jet loom as shown in Fig.1, the waste cord is produced because of the special mechanism to protect the selvage from loosing [4]. Figures 2 (a) and (b) show the recovery bucket of waste cord laying by loom's side and the aspect of gathered waste cords, respectively. For example, we have 200-250 ton/month of waste cord in Fukui prefecture having a 50% market share in synthetic textile industry in Japan. About 80 % of the waste cord consists of polyester and the rest is nylon 6. In this paper the waste cord of polyester fabric was used for the matrix material of glass/carbon hybrid composites. The continuous glass fiber bundle (Kanebo G37 1/0) and carbon fiber bundle (Toray Toreca T400B) were used for the reinforcements. Measured masses of used waste cord of polyester, glass fiber bundle and carbon fiber bundle were 0.82g/m, 0.14g/m, and 0.40g/m, respectively.

INJECTION MOLDING SYSTEM AND MOLDING METHOD

The waste cord of fabrics has a small thermal conductivity because of its porous medium. The injection molding method is advantageous for melting such material and for mixing it with reinforcements. The plastic waste such as pet bottle is usually recycled to the pellet-type resin, and the waste cord of polyester used here also can be molded to the pellet. However, there is

Fig.1 Water jet loom

(a) Recovery bucket

(b) Gathered waste cords

Fig.2 Waste cords of synthetic fabrics

a disadvantage of the heat degradation of the resin as a result of the added heating process for recycling. If the usual pellet-type resin is used as a molding material of hybrid composites, the mixing process of pellets with glass and carbon fibers is necessary beforehand. Moreover, the size of pellet limits the length of reinforcement. Therefore the pellet-type resin may be unsuitable for the injection molding of hybrid composites with longer fiber reinforcements. For above reasons, in this paper, the waste cord of polyester fabrics was fed into the injection molding machine directly together with the continuous reinforcements. Figures 3 (a) and (b) show the aspects of injection molding machine with roles for waste cord and reinforcements and the feeding zone of materials, respectively. It was cleared from a preliminary experiment that the waste cord and reinforcements were fed into the machine automatically, because the rotating screw caught the waste cord mechanically at the feeding zone. By using the present system, the reinforcement content of hybrid composites can be easily changed by regulating the feeding numbers of waste cord and reinforcements. The brief conditions of injection molding test are shown in Table 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Attention is first focused upon the tensile strength of the test piece molded from the polyester waste cord which will be a matrix material of hybrid composites. Figure 4 shows the molded tensile test piece. As expected, the test piece becomes white color because of the containing titanium in the waste cord which is used as the anti-gloss material for the fabrics. The tensile strength was measured at an ambient temperature using Shimazu Autograph AG-10TB universal testing machine along the lines of standard procedure JIS K7113 [5]. Table 2 shows the measured tensile strength for the representative five test pieces molded by using the virgin pellet,

Fig.3 Injection molding system

Table 1 Molding conditions for experiments

Back pressure (Pa)	7.84×10^5
Suckback pressure (Pa)	2.94×10^6
Injection rate (mm/s)	33
Injection pressure (Pa)	6.86×10^6
Holding pressure (Pa)	1.96×10^6
Mold clamping force (N)	2.65×10^5

Fig.4 Molded test specimen (PET)

Table 2 Tensile strength of molded test specimens

No.	(MPa)		
	Virgin pellet	Small bundle	Large bundle
1	55.6	43.8	52.1
2	55.6	44.0	56.1
3	55.4	48.8	52.9
4	56.0	48.5	53.4
5	54.9	45.5	53.2
Average	55.5	46.1	53.5
σ	0.4	2.2	1.4

σ : Standard deviation

bundle with ten waste cords (eq. small bundle) and bundle with twenty waste cords (eq. large bundle), respectively. The average value 55.5 MPa for the virgin pellet agrees well with the value 56 MPa for polyester given in the literature [6] and the value for waste cord of large bundle is nearly equal to those data. It should be noted, however, that the satisfactory strength can not be achieved for the waste cord of small bundle. This result may be caused by the heat degradation of the resin based on the longer feeding time and the defective heat transfer from heated barrel to the resin in the injection machine for the small bundle. The optimum conditions of the injection molding for the waste cord will be discussed in detail in our next paper. Thus it is concluded here that the thermoplastic products can be molded by using the waste cord of synthetic fabric such as polyester. As an advanced recycling technique, the thermoplastic composites using the waste cord as a matrix material are expected to be molded by the present injection molding system.

Attention will now be turned to the results of molded carbon/glass hybrid composite materials. In the experiments, the bundle of polyester with twenty waste cords was fed into the injection molding machine with bundle of carbon/glass reinforcements. The content of carbon/glass reinforcements W_f was fixed at 20% by weight throughout the experiments. An example of the molded test piece of hybrid composite is shown in Fig.5. As expected, the test piece becomes black color under the influence of the carbon fibers.

The measured metering times during the injection molding process for each test piece are shown in Table 3. The data indicated here are equivalent to the required times to melt the waste cord which

Fig.5 Molded test specimen (hybrid composite)

Table 3 Metering time for each composite

No.	Wfc						(sec.)	
		0	0.25	0.5	0.75	1.0	Polyester only	Virgin pellet
1		8.37	15.10	9.56	10.41	12.32	11.08	3.42
2		9.88	11.14	9.71	9.62	9.23	11.25	3.43
3		11.42	9.28	9.50	9.03	9.58	12.95	3.34
4		8.44	9.29	7.98	8.19	11.08	10.07	3.30
5		10.52	11.13	10.12	12.64	13.19	10.93	3.26
6		7.13	8.77	8.33	7.22	8.25	10.83	3.32
7		9.22	8.96	8.41	9.51	9.74	10.78	3.37
8		8.26	8.99	9.73	14.39	10.15	10.77	3.38
9		9.23	10.36	9.45	10.06	10.17	11.89	3.40
10		8.59	9.25	9.98	8.72	11.72	10.93	3.40
Ave.		9.11	10.23	9.31	9.98	10.54	11.15	3.37
σ		1.18	1.83	0.73	2.01	1.44	0.74	0.053

σ : Standard deviation

is needed for one shot of injection molding. Wfc in the table means the weight fraction of carbon fiber existing in the carbon/glass reinforcements measured before molding. Namely, Wfc=0 and 1.0 represent the glass fiber and carbon fiber reinforced composites, respectively. Few variations in data were achieved for the results of virgin pellet without reinforcements. This means that the stable thermal history during the melting process is obtained for each molding cycle. It is noted here, however, that the metering times for both waste cord and hybrid composites vary widely and the melting process of these materials takes longer time than that for the virgin pellet. The variation in metering times may be caused by the resultant unstable feeding of waste cord at the screw surface of the injection machine. It is necessary to improve the screw configuration for the advanced injection molding using the waste cord. Short metering time will be achieved by increasing the number of feeding waste cords.

The tensile strength and modulus were measured using the said AG-10TB for the molded test piece of hybrid composites. After tensile test, the fracture surfaces were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The configuration of reinforcements in the test piece was also observed after burning up the matrix resin. The resultant mass 'm' and the volume fraction of reinforcements Vf are plotted in Fig.6 as a function of Wfc. A small variations in mass may be caused by the unsettled weight fraction of reinforcements based on the unstable feeding process.

Fig.6 Mass and fiber volume fraction of hybrid composites (Wf=20 wt %)

Under the condition of fixed content by weight of carbon/glass reinforcements, the mass is sensitive to the weight fraction of each reinforcement as shown in the figure. Namely, it decreases with increasing W_{fc} , and larger volume fraction of carbon/glass reinforcements is achieved at larger value of W_{fc} because of the smaller density of carbon fiber than that of glass fiber.

The tensile strength σ_H and modulus E_H of hybrid composites are plotted against W_{fc} in Figs. 7 and 8, respectively. Figures contain 5-10 data for each case of W_{fc} . The values of σ_H and E_H increases with increasing W_{fc} , and the linear variation between the results for $W_{fc}=0$ and $W_{fc}=1$ is obtained with a small variations in data. The solid lines represents the fit of Eqs. (1) and (2) expressed as follows;

$$\sigma_H = \sigma_c \cdot W_{fc} + \sigma_g \cdot (1 - W_{fc}) \tag{1}$$

$$E_H = E_c \cdot W_{fc} + E_g \cdot (1 - W_{fc}) \tag{2}$$

where, σ_c , E_c and σ_g , E_g are the average tensile strength and modulus for $W_{fc}=1$ (i.e. carbon

Fig.7 Tensile strength σ_H of hybrid composites ($W_f=20$ wt %)

Fig.8 Tensile modulus E_H of hybrid composites ($W_f=20$ wt %)

fiber reinforced composite) and for $W_{fc}=0$ (i.e. glass fiber reinforced composite), respectively. The agreement of experimental data with the estimated values from Eqs. (1) and (2) is seen to be generally very good. The relatively large variations in data of strength may be caused by the unstable resultant contents of reinforcements and the poor fiber-matrix adhesion being due to the insufficient molding condition in the heating barrel.

The representative relation between load P and displacement of cross head δ for hybrid composites during the tensile test with 115mm span length are presented in Fig.9. It is noted from the figure that the hybrid composites fracture at smaller displacement with larger value of W_{fc} .

Figures 10 (a) and (b) show the SEM micrographs of the typical fracture surface of the hybrid composite for $W_{fc}=0.5$. The carbon fibers were recognized as relatively thicker materials in the figures. As can be seen in Fig.10 (a) for edge portion, the fiber well oriented to the material flow direction in the mold, and the pull-out of the reinforcements occurred. It is noted, however, that the fibers oriented randomly and some of fibers were not covered with resin in the center along the thickness direction as shown in Fig.10 (b) for core portion. The higher strength can be expected if the molding technique to achieve the well oriented reinforcements in the center is developed in advanced research.

Fig.9 Relation between load P and displacement δ during tensile test ($W_f=20$ wt %)

(a) Edge portion

(b) Core portion

Fig.10 SEM micrographs of fracture surface ($W_{fc}=0.5$)

Fig.11 Configuration of reinforcements

Figure 11 shows the configuration of reinforcements after molding, which is obtained by burning the matrix resin. We can see many fibers with over 10 mm length. Consequently, it is noted here that the hybrid composite with longer reinforcements can be obtained by our injection molding method of direct feeding of continuous reinforcements with matrix material.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the above results, conclusions on the recyclability of waste cord of synthetic fibers are as follows.

The injection molding method in which the waste cords are fed directly in the machine, is effective for the material recycle of waste cord of synthetic fabrics. The hybrid composite materials with high tensile strength and modulus are easily molded by using the waste cord of synthetic fabrics as a matrix material. The presented injection molding method is advantageous for the composite materials with longer fiber reinforcements.

The synthetic fibers are used for many fields such as nonwoven fabrics and fishing net, and many waste cords are produced during their manufacturing process. The injection molding method presented here must contribute to the material recycle of those waste cords.

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